

Speculation on $p = \hbar/\text{wavelength}$ For Light Emerging from Reflection from a Moving Mirror

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The relationship $p = \hbar/\text{wavelength}$ is well known for a photon. It follows from a solution for a photon from Maxwell's electromagnetic equations together with averaging. In this note we ask whether this relationship also emerges directly from a physical problem, namely reflection of light from a mirror moving at a constant velocity v . In such a case the angle of incidence does not equal that of reflection. In (1) a relationship between the reflection angle and incident angle is obtained using Fermat's principle. In (2) a relationship between the reflected wavelength and the incident wavelength is obtained in terms of v, c and the incident angle. In (3) we noted that like with Snell's law derivation, one may use conservation of momentum of light parallel to the mirror surface. Thus one has an independent approach to find the reflected angle in terms of the incident angle and two approaches, one linking the magnitude of the incident wavelength to the reflected wavelength the second, the incident momentum magnitude to the reflected one. In this note we ask whether this allows one to conclude that $p = \hbar/\text{wavelength}$.

We organize the note in the following manner. First we speculate on the form $p_i \sin(AA) = p_r \sin(BB)$ ((1)) where p_i and p_r are incident and reflected momenta and AA and BB incident and reflected angles relative to a normal to the mirror surface. We try to argue that such a form may follow from time reversal and also speculate that a similar form should hold for the wavelength to a power of 1 or -1. This then yields $p = \hbar/\text{wavelength}$.

A second approach (as performed in (3)) is to check directly if ((1)) is compatible with the wavelength relationship if $p = \hbar/\text{wavelength}$ based on the various relationships given in (1) and (2).

The Form $p_i \sin(AA) = p_r \sin(BB)$

Consider incident light with momentum (magnitude) p_i hitting a mirror moving at a constant velocity v with angle AA to the normal (to the mirror surface). p_r and BB are the reflected momentum and angle respectively. Conservation of momentum parallel to the mirror surface yields:

$$p_i \sin(AA) = p_r \sin(BB) \quad ((1))$$

We ask: Is it possible to obtain ((1)) without the knowledge of conservation of momentum by using time reversal? In particular playing the movie backwards means that p_r and BB are the incident values and p_i and AA the reflected ones. This suggests an equation symmetric in the two sets of values. Furthermore if $v=0$ i.e. the mirror is stationary the result is:

$$\text{Angle of incidence} = \text{Angle of reflection} \quad (\text{momentum is gone}) \quad ((2))$$

There is no other momentum value in the problem other than p_i and p_r , one only knows v which is a velocity. Thus we argue that one may assume a linear p_i and p_r i.e.

$$P_i \text{ Function}(AA) = P_r \text{ Function}(BB) \quad ((3))$$

For $v=0$, one has ((2)). Furthermore $\text{Function}(AA)$ should be periodic in the angle, but there are many periodic functions.

A main point that we argue is that a very similar equation should hold for the wavelength as time reversal holds for it as well. In this case one has a choice of using:

$$\text{Wavelength or } 1/\text{wavelength} \quad ((4))$$

Because both are to the power of 1. In principle one may have a different function of AA i.e.

$$1/\text{wavelength}(i) \text{ Function}_2(AA) = 1/\text{wavelength}(r) \text{ Function}_2(BB) \quad ((5))$$

We choose $1/\text{wavelength}$ due to the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ which suggests that p scales x as $1/\text{length}$.

In the above we wish to have the same units on both sides and so choose the simplest form of momentum and wavelength to the first power.

Fermat's Principle

Equations ((3)) and ((5)) introduce two different functions of AA and BB, the incident and reflected angles (and deal with momentum and wavelength). The question then arises: How does one link AA to BB? In (1) Fermat's principle is used, but this approach minimizes the time traveled by light. It is not linked to momentum or wavelength, only the speed of light and v the speed of the mirror together with AA and BB enter into the solution. A relationship between AA and BB is found, in other words a single relationship. We thus argue that there is no need for two functions $\text{Function}(AA)$ and $\text{Function}_2(AA)$ in ((3)) and ((5)) i.e. one should suffice. In fact, for $v \rightarrow 0$ it would be good to have:

$$\text{Function}(AA) - \text{Function}(BB) = 0 \quad \text{match the relationship obtained from Fermat's principle}$$

In particular that relationship is:

$$\sin(AA) - \sin(BB) = -v/c \sin(AA+BB) \quad ((6))$$

Thus for $v=0$, $\sin(AA) = \sin(BB)$ and we suggest that:

$$\text{Function}(AA) = \sin(AA) \quad ((7))$$

This then leads to conservation of momentum parallel to the mirror surface from ((3)) and $p=\text{constant}/\text{wavelength}$ from ((5)). Here we have assumed that p is not proportional to

wavelength and have chosen $1/\text{wavelength}$ instead. (This choice is linked to the Lorentz invariant $-Et+px$ which suggests that p goes as $1/\text{length}$ as noted.)

Direct Approach

Given that one has a direct expression for $\text{wavelength}(i) / \text{wavelength}(r)$ and a relationship for AA and BB (from (1) and (2)), one may check if ((1)) is consistent with these (as has been done in (3)).

In particular:

$$\text{wavelength}(r) / \text{wavelength}(i) = (1-vv/cc) / \{1 - 2(v/c) \cos(AA) + vv/cc\} \quad ((8))$$

And

$$\cos(BB) = \{-2v/c + (1+vv/cc) \cos(AA)\} / \{1 - 2(v/c) \cos(AA) + vv/cc\} \quad ((9))$$

One may note that ((8)) and ((9)) have the same denominator on the RHS.

By squaring ((1)) and replacing $\sin(AA)\sin(AA) = 1-\cos(AA)\cos(AA)$ and using ((8)) assuming:

$$p_i/p_r = \text{wavelength}(r) / \text{wavelength}(i) \quad (\text{actually the square of this})$$

One may show that the two are compatible i.e. $p=\hbar/\text{wavelength}$ and momentum parallel to the mirror is conserved.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to present two ways to argue that $p=\hbar/\text{wavelength}$ (with \hbar being treated as a constant). The first uses the idea of time reversal and also makes use of Fermat's principle. The second uses results from the literature (1) for the incident angle in terms of the reflected and the another result for the reflected wavelength in terms of the incident (2) to show that these are compatible with $p_i \sin(AA) = p_r \sin(BB)$ where p_i and p_r are incident and reflected momentum magnitudes and AA and BB the incident and reflected angles.

References

1. Gjurhcinovskci, A. Einstein's Mirror and Fermat's Principle of least time (Am. J. of Phys 72 (10) Oct. 2004)
http://muj.optol.cz/~richterek/data/media/ref_str/gjurhcinovski2004.pdf

2. Gjurhcinovski, A. The Doppler Effect from a Uniformly Moving Mirror (2004 or later)
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/physics/0409014.pdf>

3. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Alternative to Fermat's Principle for a Moving Mirror?
(preprint, zenodo, 2022)